

A PROPER TREATMENT OF INTERFACIAL CRACKS IN THE PRESENCE OF FRICTION

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SUMMARY: Frictional sliding on interface crack surfaces results in weak crack tip stress singularity and zero strain energy release rate. A new fracture criterion based on finite extension strain energy release rate is proposed to capture the intrinsic fracture toughness. The finite extension strain energy release rate is shown to represent the magnitude of the singular stress field. Numerical simulation of a center crack in a bimaterial infinite media under remote shear as well as fiber pull-out and push-out are presented to illustrate the frictional effect in both small and large scale contacts near the crack tip.

KEYWORDS: friction, fracture, interfacial crack, crack tip stress singularity, strain energy release rate, toughness, fiber pull-out and push-out

INTRODUCTION

The development of classical fracture mechanics is based on the open crack assumption, i.e., the crack surfaces are not in contact. That assumption leads to, in linear elastic solids, stress singularity of inverse square root that enables one to employ either strain energy release rate or stress intensity factor to characterize fracture toughness and predict crack movement.

When crack surfaces are under combined compression and shear, the effect of sliding frictional stresses on the crack surfaces cannot always be ignored. Only in the case in which the neartip contact zone is extremely small, the K-dominated field basically agrees with that of the open crack solution. This was discussed in detail by Sun and Qian [1] for bimaterial interfacial cracks under "Mode I" loading. On the other hand, if the contact zone is finite, frictional contact of the crack surfaces can no longer be neglected. Most importantly, the frictional contact alters the stress singularity to weak singularities [2]. Consequently, the strain energy release rate as conventionally defined vanishes [3] and cannot be used as a fracture parameter.

Many researchers have attempted to extend the fracture mechanics approach to treat various engineering problems involving interfacial cracks with frictional contact. Fiber pull-out and push-out problems have attracted the most attention (e.g., [4-7]). Delamination in thin film/substrate micro-electronics systems [8] and composite laminates [9] also have been investigated. Various methods were proposed by these authors to derive the strain energy release rate or to employ different parameters for characterizing the interfacial crack toughness. Many of these approaches suffer deficiencies mainly due to the weak singularity and the energy dissipation associated with the frictional sliding of crack surfaces.

In this study, the concept of strain energy release rate for interfacial cracks in the presence of friction is reexamined. A finite element based numerical procedure is introduced to calculate the strain energy release rate and energy dissipation due to friction for a finite crack extension. An explicit relation between the generalized stress intensity factor and the finite extension strain energy release rate is derived based on the neartip field. Thus, the finite extension strain energy release rate with a fixed crack extension can be used to represent the magnitude of the singular stress field and, therefore, to quantitatively characterize the intrinsic fracture toughness. For numerical examples, a center crack in a plane strain infinite bimaterial medium under shear loading (see Fig. 1) and fiber pull-out and push-out tests (see Fig. 2) are simulated.

Fig. 1 A bimaterial centered crack panel, 20m x 20m, under remote loading $\tau = .12\text{MPa}$

Fig. 2 Geometry and boundary condition of fiber pullout and pushout specimen. $R_f = 0.64$, $E_f = 100$, $E_m = 1$, $\nu_f = \nu_m = 0.3$, 35 % fiber in composites.

NEAR TIP FIELD AND STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE

For a crack in homogenous media with friction or an interface crack without friction, there is always square root singularity associated with the neartip field. However, it was originally shown by Comninou [2] for an interface crack between two dissimilar isotropic media with friction and later confirmed and extended by Deng [3] for an interface crack between two dissimilar anisotropic media that the stress singularity $r^{-\lambda}$ is always weak ($\lambda < 0.5$) for a static crack under monotonic loading. The singularity index λ is related to one of Dundurs parameters β and coefficient of friction μ as

$$\cot \lambda\pi = \mu\beta \tag{1}$$

It is easy to see that λ is 0.5 if β or μ is zero which corresponds to homogenous media or frictionless condition, respectively. The neartip stress field ahead of the crack tip along the bimaterial interface and the relative crack surface sliding displacement in plane strain condition are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{xy}(r,0) &= K_{II} (2\pi r)^{-\lambda} \\
 \sigma_{xy}(r,\pm\pi) &= K_{II} \cos\lambda\pi (2\pi r)^{-\lambda} \\
 \sigma_{yy}(r,\pm\pi) &= -K_{II}\beta \sin\lambda\pi (2\pi r)^{-\lambda} \\
 \Delta u_x(r) &= u_x(r,\pi) - u_x(r,-\pi) = \left[K_{II}\gamma \sin\lambda\pi / 2(1-\lambda)(2\pi)^\lambda \right] r^{1-\lambda}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

where the generalized stress intensity factor K_{II} is defined as

$$K_{II} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} (2\pi r)^\lambda \sigma_{xy}(r,0) \tag{3}$$

$$\gamma = \left[\frac{((3-4\nu_1)(1-\beta) + (1+\beta))}{2\mu_1} \right] + \left[\frac{((3-4\nu_2)(1+\beta) + (1-\beta))}{2\mu_2} \right] \tag{4}$$

In Eqn (4), μ_i and ν_i are the shear modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively, for material i ($i = 1,2$).

It has been pointed out by Dundurs and Comninou [10] that the problem of interface crack with friction is a linear process in the context of monotonic loading. In this context, relation of the strain energy release rate and stress intensity factor can be obtained through a finite crack extension Δa as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{G}(\Delta a) &= \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \int_0^{\Delta a} \left[\sigma_{xy}(r,0) - \sigma_{xy}(\Delta a - r, \pi) \right] \Delta u_x(\Delta a - r) dr \\
 &= \frac{K_{II}^2 \gamma \sin\lambda\pi}{4(1-\lambda)(2\pi)^{2\lambda}} \Delta a^{1-2\lambda} \left[\frac{\Gamma(2-\lambda)\Gamma(1-\lambda)}{\Gamma(3-2\lambda)} - \frac{\cos\lambda\pi}{2(1-\lambda)} \right]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

In Eqn (5), Γ is the gamma function.

The conventional strain energy release rate is defined as $G = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \hat{G}(\Delta a)$. It is seen from Eqn (5) that strain energy release rate G vanishes as $\Delta a \rightarrow 0$ due to the fact that $\lambda < 0.5$ in the presence of friction.

FINITE ELEMENT PROCEDURE FOR ENERGY CALCULATION

The finite element method is used to perform the energy calculation during crack extension. A two-step release technique is recommended so that self-similar mesh along the entire crack surface is not needed in calculating strain energy release rate as well as dissipation energy rate during crack extension. In calculating the strain energy release rate at the crack tip of finite contact, special care should be taken to separate the elastic nodal force from the frictional nodal force due to crack surface frictional traction near the crack tip.

In view of the foregoing, a procedure to calculate the strain energy release rate and dissipation energy rate based on crack tip nodal forces and displacements is presented. A two-step crack release method is used to allow non-self-similar mesh along the crack surface. Contact element is used behind and ahead of crack tip. For four-noded elements, the strain energy

release rate $\hat{G}(\Delta a)$ and dissipation energy rate $G_d(\Delta a)$ can be calculated as

$$\hat{G}(\Delta a) = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \left(F_x^a - \mu F_y^a \right) \left(\Delta u_x^{(2)} - \Delta u_x^{(1)} \right)$$

$$G_d(\Delta a) = G_d^N(\Delta a) + G_d^e(\Delta a) \quad (6)$$

$$G_d^N(\Delta a) = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \mu F_y^a \left(\Delta u_x^{(2)} - \Delta u_x^{(1)} \right)$$

where $G_d^e(\Delta a)$ is the portion of the dissipation energy rate from existing crack surface, and $G_d^N(\Delta a)$ is the portion of the dissipation energy rate from the new crack surface. F_x^a and F_y^a are the nodal forces at crack tip node “a” (see Fig. 3). Superscripts 1 and 2 in Eqn (6) stand for the states before and after crack release, respectively.

Fig. 3: Bimaterial crack and its coordinate system

A center crack lying between two dissimilar infinite isotropic media under remote shear loading (see Fig. 1) is used to illustrate the validity of the aforementioned technique. The commercial code ABAQUS is used to perform the analysis. The size of the panel is 20m \times 20m with a finite crack of 2m. The Dundurs parameters β and coefficient of friction μ are chosen to be 0.5. A similar problem of infinite plate was also investigated by Dundurs and Comninou [10] using elastic dislocation approach. The stress intensity factor obtained by calculating the strain energy release rate and using the relation in Eqn (5) for closed crack tip (right tip in Fig. 1) is given together with those from Dundurs and Comninou [10] in Table 1. There is excellent agreement between these two methods, and the difference is believed to be due to the finite size effect of the panel in the present study compared with the infinite medium in Dundurs and Comninou’s study.

Table 1: Comparison of stress intensity factor K_{II} from present analysis and K_{II}^d obtained by Comninou, et al. [10], $\bar{K}_{II} = (1 + \mu^2 \beta^2) K_{II} / \tau(2a)^\lambda$, $\mu = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$

$\Delta a / a$	\bar{K}_{II} (present)	$\left (K_{II} - K_{II}^d) / K_{II}^d \right \times 100\%$
$3.18 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.9723	1.28
$1.59 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.9720	1.25
$7.96 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.9724	1.29
$3.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.9737	1.42

A FRACTURE CRITERION

For the center cracked problem as discussed in the previous section, it is recognized that there is always a sizable contact zone at one crack tip (denoted as closed crack tip), and an extremely small contact zone at the other tip (which can be virtually regarded as open crack tip) under pure shear loading. This problem is studied using the finite element procedure to understand the frictional effect on the interfacial crack under small scale as well as large scale contacts. In the finite element analysis, the applied shear stress τ is assumed to be 0.12 MPa, $\mu_1 = 35$ MPa, $\mu_2 = 0.35$ MPa, and $\nu_1 = \nu_2 = 0.0$. These material properties yield $\beta = 0.49$.

The strain energy release rate $\hat{G}(\Delta a)$, dissipation energy rate $G_d(\Delta a)$ as well as total energy release rate $\hat{G}(\Delta a) + G_d(\Delta a)$ for the problem of Fig. 1 with $\beta = 0.49$ and $\mu = 0.5$ corresponding to various crack extensions are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for open and closed crack tips, respectively.

Fig. 4: Finite energy release rates at the open crack tip for the panel shown in Fig. 1

Fig. 5: Finite extension energy release rates at the closed crack tip for the panel shown in Fig. 1

At the open crack tip, the contact zone r_c / a is usually around 10^{-5} to 10^{-7} and can be virtually treated as an open crack tip. The modified crack closure technique can therefore be applied to calculate the strain energy release rates. It is seen in Fig. 4 that individual finite extension strain energy release rates are Δa dependent, while the total strain energy release rate as well as the dissipation energy rate remain constant for different crack extensions. It is

noted that dissipation energy rates are fairly small compared with strain energy release rate. This indicates that the frictional effect on the open crack tip is fairly small. It can also be shown that the stress distribution ahead of the open crack tip is very close to those of the oscillatory solution obtained based on traction free crack surface condition. It is concluded that frictional effect at the open crack tip is negligible. All existing approaches for the calculation of fracture parameters for bimaterial interfacial cracks are thus applicable (e.g., see Ref. 1).

As for the fracture behavior at the closed crack tip, it is clearly seen in Fig. 5 that the finite extension strain energy release rate decreases, and dissipation energy rate increases, while total energy release rate remains constant when crack extension Δa decreases. Recall the relationship between strain energy release rate and crack extension Δa in Eqn (5) that strain energy release rate indeed decreases and eventually vanishes when Δa approaches zero due to the weak stress singularity. The strain energy release rate is therefore Δa -dependent, while the increase of dissipation energy rate make up the decrease of strain energy release rate for total energy balance when Δa decreases. The implication of decreasing strain energy release rate is that the classical strain energy release rate concept is no longer valid because of its zero value. Consequently, a new finite extension strain energy release rate associated with a finite crack extension is needed to quantify the weak singular stress field ahead of the crack tip.

The decreasing behavior of strain energy release rate was also noticed by Stringfellow and Freund [8] who computed the J-integral for the frictional sliding fracture in a thin film on a substrate. It was pointed out later by Deng [3] that the path independence of J-integral no longer exists due to the crack surface traction resulting from friction, and the J-integral for a vanishingly small contour becomes zero indicating strain energy release rate also vanishes.

In view of the foregoing, a fracture criterion using the strain energy release rate \hat{G} of a critical finite crack extension Δa_0 as a fracture toughness parameter is proposed, i.e.,

$$\hat{G}(\Delta a_0) = \frac{\Delta W_e}{\Delta a} - G_d(\Delta a_0) - \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} = \hat{G}_c(\Delta a_0) \quad (7)$$

where ΔW_e , ΔU and $G_d(\Delta a_0)$ are the external work done, strain energy change and the dissipation energy rate for a crack extension of Δa_0 , respectively. From Eqn (5), it is seen that, for a fixed Δa_0 , the finite extension strain energy release rate \hat{G} has a unique relation with the generalized stress intensity factor K_{II} . The fracture criterion given by Eqn (7) states that the interfacial crack would grow if the neartip stress field reaches a certain critical state.

Note that the simple relations below

$$\frac{dU}{da} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{dW_e}{da}, \quad G = \frac{dU}{da} \quad (8)$$

between strain energy release rate, strain energy and work done in linear elastic fracture mechanics are no longer valid in the presence of friction. Table 2 shows the result obtained from the finite element analysis for the center crack problem (Fig. 1) with $\beta = 0.49$ and different coefficients of friction. It is evident that the above relations are no more valid in the presence of friction.

Table 2: Energy ratios for $\beta = 0.49$ and different coefficients of friction μ

μ	$\Delta U / \Delta W_e$	$(\Delta W_d + \hat{G}(\Delta a) \cdot \Delta a) / \Delta W_e$
0.02	0.4917	0.5084
0.2	0.4883	0.5117
0.5	0.4705	0.5295

FIBER PULL-OUT AND FIBER PUSH-OUT

The mechanical properties of the fiber/matrix interface are important in determining the mechanical behavior of fibrous composites. The local response of the fiber-matrix interface during fracture has pronounced effects on the mechanical performance and structural integrity of the composite. Fiber pull-out as well as fiber push-out are the two major methods to determine the fiber/matrix interfacial properties as well as to understand the toughening effect of fiber composites due to frictional sliding after debonding.

There have been numerous theoretical models based on fracture mechanics to analyze the fiber-matrix interface toughness and toughening effect due to fiber sliding. In these studies, classical strain energy release rate was the key fracture parameter in determining the debonding initiation and debonding progression. However, most researchers did not account for the effect of the weak interfacial stress singularity due to friction. Some researchers used approximate interfacial shear stress distributions to calculate the “strain energy release rate” assuming $G = dU / da$ (e.g. [4,6]). Consequently, none of these models can accurately characterize the intrinsic interfacial toughness. In this section we investigate the debonding process in the fiber pull-out and fiber push-out problem using the new finite extension strain energy release rate $\hat{G}(\Delta a)$.

It is noted that fiber pull-out and fiber push-out models adopted here are axisymmetric. However, It can be shown that the neartip stress field ahead of the crack tip and the characteristic equation for determining the singularity λ are exactly same as the plane strain problem. These features were noticed by Atkinson [11] who compared the elastic equilibrium equations for both axisymmetric and plane strain conditions near the crack tip. Therefore, the result of 2D plane problem is valid for fiber pull-out and push-out problem.

An axisymmetric section of the fiber-matrix-composite specimen shown in Fig. 2 is used for the present study. The fiber, matrix and the composite regions are assumed to be isotropic. The elastic moduli of the composite region are obtained using the rule of mixtures with fiber volume fraction of 35%. The Young’s moduli for the fiber and matrix are 100 units and 1 unit, respectively, and the Poisson’s ratios are assumed to be 0.3 for both. The characteristic crack extension length Δa_0 is taken to be 0.01 throughout the debonding process. Two types of loading are used for various debonding lengths; one is constant load for both fiber pull-out and push-out, the other is constant displacement loading for fiber push-out only.

An open debonding crack tip is associated with the fiber pull-out under constant load σ (see Fig. 6). The total strain energy release rate increases at initial debonding stage and become steady state after debonding length reaches two times the fiber diameter. For the open crack,

the critical strain energy release rate G_c with a mode mixity must be determined.

Fig. 6: Finite extension energy release rates for fiber pull-out under constant load σ

During fiber push-out under constant load σ , the debonding crack surface is completely closed and the frictional effect is significant. Figure 7 shows the finite extension strain energy release rate, dissipation energy rate and total energy rate for various debonding lengths. It is seen that \hat{G} and G_d increase until debonding reaches two times the fiber diameter. There is a slight decrease for both energy rate afterwards. Figure 8 gives the ratios of strain energy change in the elastic body and total external work done during crack release for two different coefficient of friction μ . It is seen that those ratios are no longer 0.5 as these in the frictionless case, especially at initial and final debonding stages. However, Eqn (8) may still be a good approximate when μ is very small.

Fig. 7: Finite extension energy release rates for fiber change and push-out under constant load σ

Fig. 8: Ratio of strain energy external work done during crack growth in fiber push-out for $\mu = 0.5$ and 0.2 .

Results for fiber push-out under constant displacement loading $u_0 = 0.2$ are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 for two coefficient of friction. It can be easily seen that the initial crack growth is unstable. Stable crack growth prevails after debonding reaches two times the fiber diameter. Besides, It is seen that there are virtually no change in total energy rate $\hat{G} + G_d$ and external applied force for different friction coefficient. However, value of \hat{G} for $\mu = 0.5$ is much smaller than that for $\mu = 0.2$. This indicates that a larger applied force is needed for larger

coefficients of friction to raise \hat{G} to the level of the critical intrinsic fracture toughness \hat{G}_c .

Fig. 9: Finite extension energy release rates for fiber push-out under constant displacement $u_0 = 0.2$ with $\mu = 0.5$.

Fig. 10: Finite extension energy release rates for fiber push-out under constant displacement $u_0 = 0.2$ with $\mu = 0.2$.

EFFECT OF COMPRESSIVE LOADING

An open crack may be forced to close if compressive loads normal to the crack surfaces are applied in addition to the shear load. This condition may exist in fiber composite due to the mismatch of coefficients of thermal expansion between the fiber and matrix. For such a closed interfacial crack, the near tip stress field has a stronger singularity, i.e., $\lambda > 0.5$ [12], and the classical strain energy release rate becomes unbounded. Consequently, the intrinsic interfacial fracture toughness must be measured in terms of the finite extension strain energy release rate for a critical distance a_0 . However, the toughnesses of the two closed cracks with stronger and weaker singularities, respectively, should not be interchanged.

CONCLUSIONS

The presence of friction on interfacial cracks lying between two dissimilar media may cause the crack surfaces to close and crack tip stress singularity to become less singular than the inverse square root singularity. Depending on the loading direction, the contact size may be extremely small or finite. For the case of small contact zones, the crack tip can be treated effectively as an open crack and the fracture criterion in terms of total strain energy release rate and mode mixity can be employed. For the case of finite contact zones, the classical strain energy release rate vanishes and thus cannot be used as a fracture parameter as in linear fracture mechanics. A strain energy release rate based on a finite crack extension is shown to be uniquely related to the near tip stress field and is capable of capturing the intrinsic fracture toughness of the interfacial crack.

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REFERENCES

1. Sun, C.T. and Qian, W., "The Use of Finite Extension Strain Energy Release Rates for Fracture in Interface Cracks," to appear in *International Journal of Solids and Structures*.
2. Comninou, M., "Interface Crack with Friction in the Contact Zone," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 44, 1977, pp. 780-781.
3. Deng, X., "An Asymptotic Analysis of Stationary and Moving Cracks with Frictional Contact along Bimaterial Interfaces and in Homogeneous Solids," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 31, No. 17, 1994, pp. 2407-2429.
4. Gao, Y. C, Mai, Y.W. and Cotterell, B., "Fracture of Fiber Reinforced Materials", *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics. (ZAMP)*, Vol. 39, 1988, pp. 550-572.
5. Sigl, L.S. and Evans, A.G., "Effects of Residual Stress and Frictional Sliding on Cracking and Pullout in Brittle Matrix Composites," *Mechanics of Materials*, Vol. 8, 1989, pp.1-12.
6. Kerans, R.J. and Parthasarathy, T.A., "Theoretical Analysis of the Fiber Pullout and Pushout Tests," *Journal of the American Ceramics Society*, Vol. 74, 1991, pp. 1585-1596.
7. Hutchinson, J.W. and Jensen, H.M., "Models of Fiber Debonding and Pullout in Brittle Composites with Friction," *Mechanics of Materials*, Vol. 9, 1990, pp. 139-163.
8. Stringfellow, R.G. and Freund, L.B., "The Effect of Interfacial Friction on the Buckle-Driven Spontaneous Delamination of a Compressed Thin Film, ," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 30, No. 10, 1993, pp. 1379-1395.
9. Buchholz, F.G., Wang, H., Ding, S. and Rikards, R., "Delamination Analysis For Cross-Ply Laminates under Bending with Consideration of Crack Face Contact and Friction," *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-10)*, Vol. 1, Whistler, BC, Canada, August 14-18, 1995, pp. 141-148.
10. Comninou, M. and Dundurs, J., "Effect of Friction on the Interface Crack Loaded in Shear," *Journal of Elasticity*, Vol. 10, No. 2, 1980, pp. 203-212.
11. Atkinson, C., Avila, J., Betz, E. and Smelser, R.E., "The Rod Pull Out Problem, Theory and Experiment," *Journal of Mechanical and Physical Solids*, Vol. 30, No. 3, 1982, pp. 97-120.
12. Qian, W. and Sun, C.T., "Frictional Interfacial Fracture under Combined Compressive and Shear Loading," to be published.